

**Philosophical Idealism: The Thoroughfare of Teaching and Learning
Mathematics Education**

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Abstract

The article is titled “Philosophical Idealism: The Thoroughfare of Teaching and Learning Mathematics Education”. Its discussion is based on how Philosophical ideas will be applied into the teaching and learning of Mathematics Education in the classroom. The discussion is centred on idealism in Philosophy, which is sub themed into three main areas of philosophy and these areas are: subjective idealism, objective idealism and scientific idealism. The article, in its conclusion solicits for the use of these philosophical ideas in the classroom by both the teacher and the learner to drive home the abstract areas of mathematics.

Keywords: Philosophical Idealism, Mathematics Education, Teaching, Learning, Subjective Idealism, Objective Idealism, Scientific Idealism,

Introduction: The Nigerian classrooms shouldn't have been a space for just the learner, teacher and infrastructures but there would have been an area in the space for teachers to talk about philosophical thoughts that will lead the learners to understanding Mathematics better. Philosophy being the principle of mind-set that acts as a guide to mankind (Britannica 2023), needs to be part of the classroom discussion any time Mathematics is being taught. In corroboration, Bebebiafiai (2006:3), opined that man's understanding of concepts and principles that are based on his love of wisdom that had led to verifying, clarifying and justifying life issues, makes way for man's life to be more meaningful and purposeful. So to make Mathematics learning more meaningful and purposeful to the learner, the philosophical ideas beg for their inclusion in the Mathematics classroom.

Mathematics Education being part of philosophical thoughts, the idea of bringing it side by side with the philosophy in the classroom is what the paper is looking at. Like Davison¹ and Mitchell² (2008), pointed out that in philosophy the absolutist sees mathematical knowledge as certain and unchallengeable while fallibilist sees it as mere revision and correction. But the facts still remain that mathematics education is beyond revision and correction, as it continues to solve human problems on earth as Karin, David, Darren and Gunter (2011) factored in mathematical modeling into hotel industry as a strategy in maximizing revenue collection.

It must have been on this premise that these thoughts of man, though interwoven, are been classified, so as to narrow down or shorten the radius of the mathematical vicious circle. And one of these classes is the school of mathematics, whose radius of its vicious circle value still has

infinity. Many works have been carried out under mathematics yet man has not gotten to the centre of the circle, not to talk of realizing the diametrical dimension.

Mathematics Education was defined by (New World Encyclopedia, 2010) in Adedeji (2018), as the policies and procedures designed to equip teachers with the knowledge, attitudes, behaviors and skills they require to perform their tasks effectively in the school and classroom. The National Policy on Education in Nigeria (FRN, 2013) cited in Odo (2010) presented the objectives of Mathematics and Mathematics Education as follows: (1) to lay a solid foundation for the concept of numeracy and scientific thinking; (2) to develop in the child the ability to adapt in his changing environment; (3) to develop manipulative skills to enable him to function effectively in the society with his capacity; (4) to prepare the learner for higher education. In their perception Etuk and Bello,(2015) asserted that the growing needs of mathematics education in science, technology, business, medicine, humanities, etc, have placed a burden on the subject-mathematics on how it would be properly taught and understood by the learner, particularly at the secondary school level. Teaching is the concerted sharing of knowledge and experience. This is usually organized within a disciple and, more generally, the provision of stimulus to the psychological and intellectual growth of a person by another person or artifact, (Impedovo and Laquinta, 2023).

On the other hand, learning according to (Bingham and Conner in Connie, 2023) is “the transformative process of taking in information that when internalized and mixed with what we have experienced, changes what we do. It’s based on input, process, and reflection. It is what changes us”.

In the light of the above reviewed contributions to knowledge, the topic ‘Philosophical Idealism: the thoroughfare of teaching and learning Mathematics Education’ is introduced as an additive philosophical knowledge on easing Mathematics teaching and learning; through the three concepts discussed under Idealism and Mathematics Education below.

Philosophical Idealism

Philosophy as a discipline is compartmentalized but in the mist of all that, there are top ten philosophical ideas, that philosophers and lovers of philosophy ponder on them, from generation to generation but still have not gotten a clear cut. Questions such as ‘what is the meaning of life?’ ‘What are good and evil?’ ‘What is justice?’, were raised in ages passed, yet no convincing answers is given to man. In search of answers to these questions, many Philosophers have come up with their own perceptions of life, good, evil and justice. And this has generated to top ten perceptions (ideas) that are been philosophized. These top ten philosophical ideas are: Plato’s Theory of Ideas, the concept of introspection, the concept of solipsism, the Theodicy: the attempt to vindicate God, moral relativism, categorical imperative or the golden rule of morality, determinism/indeterminism: are our fates sealed?, cogito ergo sum: I think, therefore I am, God id dead and existential crisis: a contemporary philosophical concept (Sus, 2023). But from these various schools of philosophical ideas, the paper tends to concentrate on the Socratic idealism that has something to do with mathematics education.

Literature

Idealism which is said to be the oldest philosophical schools which cuts across both eastern and Western civilizations points, having Socrates as the founding father. Other idealists that existed after Socrates were Parmenides, Pythagoras, Plato, St. Augustine, Spinoza, Leibniz, Kant, Hegel, Berkeley to mention a few. Idealism is said to be an interpreter of human experiences and existence in terms of ideas and images conceived by the mind. As Plato in (Enukoha, Okeme, and Usono, 2007) puts it, human knowledge is nothing short of a recollection of ideas which are inborn in man. The idealists such as (Okoye,2023) believes that the Ultimate about truth is based on mental and spiritual and that is why the idealists live in two worlds—the heavenly(the world of ideas), which they believe to be perfect and earthly(the world of shadows) which is from the senses and is taken as imperfect. Its development has further classified it to three versions that have mathematics education connected and these areas are: (1) Subjective (2) Objective and (3) Scientific.

In the light of the above the detail discussion of how these three concepts of philosophical idealism are linked with the mathematics education are presented below.

Idealism and Mathematics Education

- *Subjective Idealism and Mathematic Education*
- *Objective Idealism and Mathematic Education*
- *Scientific Idealism and Mathematic Education*

Subjective Idealism and Mathematic Education

The Britannica Encyclopedia, (2022) focuses on the experiences of the mind; It holds that only mind and mental (spirit) content exist. And Knox (2023) cited Hegel said “The finite world is a reflection of mind, which alone is truly real”. John,(2020) corroborated with this fact by seeing philosophical idealism as the metaphysic that associates reality to ideas in the mind, rather than to material objects. And if this is the idea hovering around the subjective idealism, one may be tempted to ask, what has that got to do with mathematics education? Mathematics like any other subject or course needs interdependence. The bridge that links the two disciplines is the mind. The experience of the learner’s mind from previous class works matters a lot. They serve as a link road between the learner and the new knowledge to be learnt. On the other hand the mental state of the learner forms the base of the settlement of Mathematical content. Other links include:

- (1) Experience in a simple mathematical equation at the primary school level will definitely makes learning of algebraic equations in the secondary school easier to the learner.
- (2) A mathematical formula experience by the learner’s mind will certainly make the learner to follow up any computation that has a link with that formula in his subsequence exposure to mathematics learning.

It is therefore absolutely necessary for the teacher to build up this backup of the learner, by trying within his possible best to see that a good percentage of the learners understand what is been delivered at the period by preparing their minds with this philosophical idea before the main class

starts. He also has the duty of informing the learners about the experiences they are going to have from the topics being treated; that such experiences will serve as bridges to other mathematical knowledge that will use in walking to the learners' seats of knowledge; as in line with Jan-Emmanuel, (2023) submission that said, 'It seems implausible that something you have not experienced directly could make a difference to your wellbeing, if you never feel its impact, how could it affect your life?'

Objective Idealism and Mathematic Education

This idealism which is also referred to as common sense realism; its father-Kant, (1781) in Rohlf, (2010) in his transcendental idealism stated that:

human beings experience only appearance, not things in themselves, and that space and time are only subjective forms of human intuition that would not subsist in themselves if one were to abstract from all subjective conditions of human intuition

Marriam-Webster,(2022); also said, the senses provide to man direct awareness of objects as he navigates in his quiet time. In other words the mind has the ability to create from the experiences gotten through the five senses of human being. And the Mathematics Education is not in isolation from the experiences perceived from the five senses. The teacher therefore needs to emphasize to the learner that the experiences of Mathematics objects by the learner is a true reality. And the learner should know that whatever new impression gotten through any of the five senses is a true reality and it should be held onto. The perceiver of the object before he/she starts to redesign the object, he must have perceived to know how small or large the object would have being; the shape of the object, the quantities of the materials to be used in making the object, and probably the cost in acquiring the materials must have being mentally conceived. All these mathematical concepts are surrounding the objective idealism law and the learner needs to take advantage of this philosophical law in advancing his mathematical knowledge.

Scientific Idealism and Mathematic Education

This has to do with applying critical methods in humanistic and scientific studies in solving matters around man, who is seen as the creator of the world as propounded by Cohen in Scott,(2020).It is also seen as a philosophy that believes in scientific progress and improvement (Study.com, 2023). What seems to be unquestionable by man are factors being scientifically proved and this is normally done by mathematical computations; for example, two individuals who were born in two different states may want to know who is older than the other. In order to argue over it, they place the matter before a third person. For the truth to be unveiled each person states the year, month, date and time he was born. The third party on seeing the data pronounces the result and the moment they see their differences in year, month, date and time, both parties accept the result and start playing within the confines of their differences. But if it were based on mere stories or appearances, it would have resulted to an endless argument and perhaps into a fight.

Looking at it in a wider spectrum, scientific idealism would be useful when solving the problem of two or more variables in an investigation; where means, mode, median, standard deviation and many more mathematical formulas will come into play.

It is therefore mandatory for the mathematics teacher to emphasize to the learner, the importance of the use of scientific approach (which is mathematical) in solving any matter or event that comes around him/her.

Conclusion

Ideas are propounded by so many scholars to make solving matters easier for the universe but man always look for shorter ways of solving his problem and end up creating more problems than solving the problem. Therefore, teachers should be focused on any of the three ideas they feel will drive home the message they are to impact on the learner. Again, most teachers start teaching the learner from the unknown to the known; forgetting the fact that the learner has a 'tabula rasa' and needs an entry point on what you are delivering. Therefore these ideas propounded, to make learning easier, should be utilized properly by the teacher to fill that blank space (the tabula rasa) in the learner's mind for learning to be more meaningful to him/her at the period of his/her learning. As Uka and Ekweme (2012) in Odo (2018) stated concerning learning that mathematics has helped in developing modern technology through application of its principles in modern inventions and that wouldn't have taken place, if not of learning. Again, an answer to Etuk and Bello (2022) assertion is a clear indicator to the use of this philosophical idealism. The Mathematics teacher is therefore advised to use these three philosophical idealism principles to make teaching and learning easier and driving home, the objectives of the National Policy of Education (FRN, 2013) (as it concerns Mathematics Education), in the learner's life.

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